

Capacity Building and Employee Performance of Quoted Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed at investigating the association between capacity building and employee performance of quoted deposit money banks (QDMBs), Nigeria. A survey research design was employed for the study while three (3) most valued banks in Nigeria 2021 (Guarantee Trust Bank Plc, Fidelity Bank Plc, and First Bank Plc) in Nigeria were selected. The collection of data was done via a structured questionnaire and simple frequency tables and the arithmetic mean was used to analyze the data. The formulated hypotheses were tested using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and Statistical Packages for Social Science (SPSS version 23). The study revealed that there is a major association between capacity building and employee performance by indicating a relationship between technical capacity and task accomplishment; there is also a significant relationship between adaptive capacity and employee effectiveness. The study concluded that capacity building contributes to employee performance in QDMBs. The study also deduced that employees with high adaptive capacity can function in any changing situation. The study recommended that there is a need for bank management to adopt continuous leadership development programs to equip organizational leadership with the right leadership skill through quality decisions as well as compel employee commitment.

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KEYWORDS: Capacity-Building, Employee-commitment, Employee-Performance, Task- accomplishment. Technical-capacity

INTRODUCTION

The success and or otherwise of most emerging economies like Nigeria is believed to be tied to its capacity-building especially human capital build-up. Capacity building is the practice of improving individuals' and groups' knowledge, skills, and attitudes to design, develop, manage, and maintain locally relevant institutional and operational infrastructures and processes. Capacity-building may be adopted through training and development, teamwork, and organizational learning (Groot & Molen, 2015). The continuous quest for quality product and service offerings prompted the business organization to adopt modern technology in their daily operation. Organizational products may differ from one firm to another; this may be due to the knowledge management in the organization. An organization may decline in operation if the capacity does not align with the technological, societal, and environmental changes as customers are after satisfaction with the product (Ibru & Kasima, 2012). The continuous technological advancement in the banking sector may compel more attention to the capacity level of staff in a banking firm.

The introduction of technology in the Nigerian banking sector has promoted an easy banking system against the previous banking practice that is stressful. Today, customers can easily transact business from the comfort of their homes and as well do numerous bank transactions from their offices and business outlet. To this end, technological advancement has resulted in a cashless system in Nigerian financial institutions especially, the banking sector (Muogbo & Eze, 2020). Though, the system seems to reduce the workload of bankers because customers can adopt the use of a device (Phones, Laptops, POS, ATM, and other electronic devices) to withdraw, transfer and deposit cash. Focusing on the internal operating system of banks, there are a series of machines used by bank staff daily to achieve a task. These machines range from counting devices, POS, Barcode scanners and bill counter, and touch screen cash register machines. The effective use of these machines is a result of the required adoption of a continuous capacity-building mechanism.

The banking industry is stigmatized with concurrent mergers and acquisitions due to the failure of banks to adapt to changes in the internal and external environment. Banks such

as the liquidated Oceanic Bank which seems to be at the forefront of banking operation years back with quality services, high customer loyalty and a strong financial base got out of operation due to a poor lack of internal control mechanism. The standard of operation seems to vary between the former and the latter which is contrary to the expectations of stakeholders. The nature of services may be dependent on the available capacity in the organization. The contingencies that are attached to environmental changes may compel organizations to adopt capacity building to remain in a competitive and depressed business environment and adapt to turbulent business changes for greater performance.

Service quality offered by bank firms may differ from organization to organization as each bank has staff with varying capacity and job knowledge. This may be represented in the technical capacity of the firm. Technical capacity may be in the form of innovation. Innovation may be in various forms such as process innovative capacity, radical or incremental innovative capacity, and administrative or technological innovative capacity (Catherine & Pervaiz, 2014). While some bank services may be innovative inclined, fast, and reliable, other banks may be delaying and frustrating. This seems to give some firms a competitive edge over others. The degree of Technical capacity of a bank firm may affect the rate at which a task is accomplished.

It was observed that some of the failed banks (as such banks could not meet their obligations to their depositors and other stakeholders due to bad loans, capital inadequacy, poor management, etc) were rated high at the time of existence by customers but seized to exist at the end of the day. This may be attributed to the failure to formulate an adaptive strategy to the changing demands of the environment. This is the case of former Skye which was acquired by Polaris bank Plc as the firm could not operate alongside the technological advancement in the banking sector. With more focus on adaptive capacity, the problem of survival may be minimized. In light of this, it is necessary to investigate the link between capacity building and employee performance in quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria.

This research was prompted by the increasing demand for technological advancement in the banking sector as employees tend to experience challenges in adapting to change in most bank organizations. Capacity-building may be a strategy adopted by bank management in preparation for adapting to the use of this technology. Though what seems to be a major challenge is the leadership capacity towards ensuring that employees are committed in times of change. Staff in the Teller Department of First Bank Plc reported during a survey visitation by the researcher that there is constant information flow to each staff before the adoption of a new system such as Android Point of Sale Terminal (POS service), Money note counter (A replacement to the human counting of a currency note) which is time-consuming and stressful, bill counter and touch screen cash register machine. The successful adoption of this modern technology in bank

organizations may be attributed to the degree of relationship between management capacity and employee commitment.

It was observed by the researcher that the speed of service delivery varies from one bank to another. This may be attributed to the amount of technical expertise that is available in the bank. The technical capacity of an organization relates to whether it has the necessary skills, tools, and facilities to implement programs and manage operations (Okpanel, 2013). The technical capacity may affect the rate at which tasks in accomplish in the firm.

Despite the huge financial and human materials commitment in building the capacity of both human and the institutional system by these financial institutions to remain afloat in business, QDMBs in Nigeria still face a dearth of required skills to operate effectively and efficiently, poor service delivery as customers still queue for hours before been attended to, the ineffective customer-staff relationship among others. Against this backdrop, the need to investigate the relationship between capacity building and employee performance of QDMBs in Nigeria becomes imperative.

The overall goal of this research is to see if there is a link between capacity building and employee performance in QDMBs in Nigeria. The following are the specific objectives:

- I. To identify the extent of the relationship between technical capacity and task accomplishment of QDMBs in Nigeria.
- II. To determine the degree of relationship between adaptive capacity and employee effectiveness of QDMBs in Nigeria.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

II. Conceptual Review

Capacity Building

According to Groot and Molen (2015), capacity building in business is the process of developing knowledge, required skills, and good attitudes change in individuals and groups that are pertinent to the design, idea expansion, management of interest, and maintenance of locally relevant institutional and operational infrastructures in the organization. This is a more comprehensive strategy, but it still prioritizes education, training, and human resource development. As a result, capacity development for workers in a wide sense might refer to advances in all employees' ability to do acceptable duties within the organization's larger set of performance requirements. Capacity building takes happens at three levels, according to the United Nations Committee of Experts on Public Administration (2016): individual, institutional, and social. Individual capacity building refers to the creation of situations that permits people not only to expand but improve their prevailing knowledge and capabilities. It permits people to participate in the learning and adaptation to change process (United Nations Committee of Experts on Public Administration (UNCEPA), 2016).

Capacity building has been defined in a variety of ways. Some writers have described it as a broad word that

encompasses a wide variety of activities, expertise, and resources that non-profits require to be successful, while others have concentrated on defining the capacity development process (Anoke, Nzewi & Tukura, 2022). Two meanings appear to be more often quoted in the literature than others.

It is defined by Connolly and Lukas (2012) as "a broad spectrum of competencies, expertise, and resources that charities require to be effective." When looking at definitions, keep in mind that some include conceptions of capacity that go beyond organizations. Because capacity may be created at the individual and community levels, definitions must encompass these ideas. Capacity building, according to the United Nations, is the process by which people, firms, and communities improve their abilities to perform essential duties, solve tasking challenges, set and attain organizational goals; comprehend and fulfill their developmental requirements in a wide and long-term manner (Management Development and Governance Division, United Nations Development Program, 2011).

Technical Capacity

This relates to whether the organization has the necessary talents, tools, and facilities to provide its programs and run its business. Specific technological capacity areas, according to Okpanel (2014), include:

i. Technology: Having the essential resources (equipment, systems, software, etc.) to run the business efficiently.

ii. Technology skills: The capacity to operate efficiently.

iii. Program Design and Review - The capacity to plan and carry out a thorough evaluation. This refers to the technical abilities required to create a correct program design as well as an appropriate program logic model or other assessment tools that may assess programming effectiveness. This is not the same as using the evaluation findings to continue learning and improving. The notion of evaluation for continual learning, whether programmatic or organizational, is covered separately below.

iv. Marketing abilities: The ability to successfully interact with both internal and external stakeholders.

v. Fund-raising abilities: The capacity to get the financial and in-kind resources required to run a successful business.

Capability in terms of technology might take the shape of creativity. Process innovative capacity, radical or incremental innovative capacity, and administrative or technological innovative capacity are all examples of different types of innovation (Okpanel, 2014).

Adaptive Capacity

The ability of an organization to monitor, analyze, respond to, and produce internal and external changes is known as adaptive capacity (Okpanel, 2014). In this area of organizational capability, the conception of a "learning

organization" is captured. It was claimed that renowned field leaders focus on an organization's capacity to "do things" to achieve, perform, or be effective in executing activities that support the organization's goals, mission, and sustainability. For example, Dougherty (2013) defines organizational capacity as "the combined effect of an organization's skills to govern and manage itself, generate assets and resources, form the correct community links, and offer valuable services—all combining to meaningfully fulfill its goal."

Adaptability may be described as a successful shift in response to a changing situation (Kyap, 2015). Adaptability refers to an organization's ability to effectively analyze emerging business issues, and implement essential advances and enhancements to its products, services, business, structures, management style, business processes, models, and strategies to adapt and thrive in the face of new changes (Banterhe, Carrares & Cavaliere, 2011). Business Adaptive Capacity offers the groundwork for a businessperson to boost and harvest from innovative dynamics and intellectual capabilities (Stefano, Peteraf, and Verona, 2010). Firms must be skilled in four basic capabilities: environmental scanning, accurate perceiving of opportunities and threats, prompt responding to signals, experimenting, managing a multi-complex structure, and mobilizing required resources (Reeves and Deomler, 2011). The employment of a more complex and organized information guttering by an analytic system improves organizations' ability to read, detect, and respond to signals. The focus of this procedure is frequently on recognizing the indications indicating a need for immediate and rapid change (Reeves & Deimber, 2011). Not only must strategic and operational intervention be made in real-time, but it must also attempt to bypass the typical stone-cold rational decision-making procedures and hierarchies (Reeves and Deimber, 2011).

Employee Performance

Cascio (2012) defines performance as an employee's capacity to carry out specific obligations. In other words, underperformance must be based on some performance expectations. An employee performance analysis is hanged on the difference between employee performance, set criteria, and individual strengths and weaknesses in terms of personal characteristics and delivery abilities (Goss, 2014). Individual assessments must then be completed, followed by a development plan, to attain improved productivity and a results-oriented team.

Employee performance is said to improve when workers' skills and talents develop. While there are few thorough studies on the major link between staff development programs and better performance, a small number of studies do suggest that they can enhance performance. Employee performance is determined by the employees' willingness to complete their jobs as well as their openness to doing so (Sinha, 2011). Furthermore, according to Sinha (2011), having people that are willing and open to execute their jobs

can boost productivity, which leads to better performance (Sinha, 2011). The capacity to perform, as well as the opportunity and inclination to perform, can be used to assess an employee's performance. The desire of employees to put out as much effort as possible in their jobs is referred to as eagerness to perform (Eysenck, 2015).

Task Accomplishment

Task accomplishment refers to actions that are part of the formal reward system (i.e., technical core) and meet the job requirements (Williams and Karau, 2011). Task completion, in general, refers to the outcomes of translating materials into the commodities and services generated by the organization or allowing the organization to run efficiently (Motowidlo, 2013). As a result, job completion includes meeting the conditions outlined in the employer-employee contract. Furthermore, job completion is a multi-dimensional entity. Campbell (1990), as mentioned in (Motowidlo, 2013), advocated an eight-factor hierarchical model. Five of which have to do with the completion of work- job-specific task competence, non-job-specific task proficiency, writing, and spoken communication skills, supervision (in the event of a leadership post); and, to a lesser extent, management/administration. Each of these five criteria has sub-factors that are significant for different vocations. The supervision aspect, for example, comprises (1) mentoring, directing, and motivating subordinates, as well as providing feedback, maintaining strong working relationships, and coordinating subordinates and other resources to complete the task (Anoke and Ibrahim, 2022).

Employee Effectiveness

An employee is effective if he meets the company's objectives (William, 2015). Only businesses with well-defined, time-sensitive, quantifiable, and operational goals may apply this technique. Only a few employees are said to satisfy these requirements in the literature on organizational effectiveness. Even yet, determining an employee's success without tying it to the organization's goals, even if these aren't well defined, is challenging. In general, the goal-setting process represents senior management's and shareholders' perspectives on effectiveness (Lodewijk, 2016). Employee effectiveness has a significant impact on organizational effectiveness. Jorge (2014) defined organizational effectiveness as an organization's ability to achieve its goals efficiently. This refers to a company that achieves a targeted result or is productive without wasting resources.

Effectiveness, according to Jaharkanti (2014), is defined as the efficient, effective, and strategic use of all organizational resources, including human, financial, and technology resources, to achieve a competitive advantage. Organizational efficiency also necessitates achieving long-term growth and development by considering not only the expectations of shareholders but also those of other stakeholders. Leadership, Communication, Accountability, Delivery, Performance, and Measurement are among the six

(6) systems of organizational effectiveness described by Robert and William (2015). These six system frames assist individuals to understand how everything works together to meet the organization's goals.

Theoretical Framework

This research was based on Paulis' Scenistic Theory of Capacity Building. According to the theory, capacity development is a method that targets specific performance difficulties, requirements, and shortfalls by concentrating on scenarios, events, case studies, and narratives. However, because of the social engagement and consolidation practice required, as well as cost and efficacy considerations, the scientific approach to capacity building is better suited to team training rather than solo teaching. The Scenic theory of capacity building defined organizational capacity levels, which included situated learning/cognition, constructivism and experiential learning, transformational learning, and action approaches.

Relevance of Scenic Theory of Capacity Building to the Study

In this study, the Scenic theory of capacity building holds water since it showed the value of capacity building to employee performance. The hypothesis suggested that the sort of capability needed depends on the perceived gap in the organization. According to the idea, learners' suitability for the training process, as well as their contribution to training efficacy, is critical. This is contingent on their inventiveness and their capacity to develop their decision-making and delegating skills, all of which are enhanced by the transformational learning method. The idea provided certain rules that have helped to govern individual behavior and attain training goals.

Empirical Review

Claussen (2016) conducted a study on capacity building for organizational success at United Way of Calgary and Area (UWCA). The study used secondary data, and the findings suggested that there is minimal concern for organizational effectiveness capacity building. The study found that capacity building had a beneficial impact on organizational effectiveness. The research concluded that the organization's organizational capacity should be built regularly.

Denmark (2015) conducted research to better understand capacity building and the characteristics of land administration systems. The research was based on a review of the literature on capacity building and land administration. According to the findings, there are three stages of capacity building: overall system capacity, organizational capacity, and group capacity. According to the findings, capacity building is an important steam component that should be handled right now rather than later. As a result, the study suggests that land administration systems be seen as capacity-building initiatives in and of themselves, to increase

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institutional capacity to satisfy medium- and long-term demands.

As a review, Coetzee (2015) looked at the components of organizational commitment. Affective commitment, normative commitment, and continuation commitment were studied as components of commitment. The researchers discovered a strong link between the components of commitment and organizational work behavior. In addition, the study found a link between commitment and corporate citizenship behavior. Personal variables, environmental factors, work features, and subordinate-supervisor interpersonal interaction were found to be predictors of employee commitment behavior in the study.

Suhag, Solangi, Larik, Lakho, and Tagar (2017) explored the correlation between knowledge retention and telecommunications company performance. Process innovation, talent retention, and organizational innovation are independent variables, with organizational culture acting as a moderator. The study is a survey in which a questionnaire is given to 200 workers in Islamabad and Rawalpindi who are interested in telecom sector innovation. SPSSv.20 software was used to analyze the data. Talent retention, process innovation, and organizational innovation all have a favorable influence on company success.

In West Java, Indonesia, Hilmiana, and Muizu (2017) investigated the impact of personality on group capacity building and emotional intelligence in rural banks. A cross-sectional research approach was used in this study. The research sample consisted of 233 people who were chosen via

proportionate random selection. In Smart PLS software, the PLS-SEM analytic approach (Partial Least Square - Structural Equation Modeling) is used in the study analysis. The findings revealed that personality has a substantial impact on group capacity growth. Emotional intelligence can also be enhanced by a person's personality. The findings also revealed that employee desire to learn on the job had an impact on group capacity. Employees with a high degree of emotional intelligence have an impact on employee readiness to learn and employee relationships in the workplace, according to the research. Employees with a high degree of emotional intelligence, as measured by personal and social competence, are more likely to be engaged in their job as well as their organization or firm, according to the research. According to the survey, the organization should be able to use an effective group learning technique to increase employee engagement.

III. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a survey research design since it involves eliciting data from the subject of the study. The population is 386 staff of the three most valued QDMBs in Nigeria as of December 2021. According to Nigeria Stock Exchange, the 3 Nigerian banks with the highest market value are Guarantee Trust Bank Plc; First Bank Plc and Fidelity Bank Plc. The survey was narrowed to the sampled banks branches in Awka, Anambra state for convenience and timely completion of the study. All the branches of the sampled banks in Awka were covered by the researchers. The distributions are as follows

Table3.1: List of sampled QDMBs, Staff Positions and Staff Strength

Bank	Branch Locations	Staff Positions	Staff Strength	
Guarantee Trust Bank Plc	Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.	Senior Staff	9	
		Junior Staff	18	
		Non-Core Staff	26	
	Total =53			
	Eke-Awka, Awka	Senior Staff	8	
		Junior Staff	12	
		Non-Core Staff	18	
	Total =38			
	GTB Total			=91
Fidelity Bank Plc	Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.	Senior Staff	6	
		Junior Staff	14	
		Non-Core Staff	26	
		Total	= 46	
	Regina Caeli Junction, Awka.	Senior Staff	6	
		Junior Staff	11	
		Non-Core Staff	21	
		Total	=38	
	Ziks Avenue, Awka	Senior Staff	4	
		Junior Staff	10	
		Non-Core Staff	19	
		Total	=33	

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		Fidelity Total	=117
First Bank Plc	Ziks Avenue	Senior Staff	6
		Junior Staff	9
		Non-Core Staff	15
		Total	=30
	Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.	Senior Staff	11
		Junior Staff	15
		Non-Core Staff	30
		Total	56
	Enugu-Onitsha Expressway, Awka.	Senior Staff	8
		Junior Staff	14
		Non-Core Staff	26
		Total	48
	Ukwu-oji, Awka	Senior Staff	6
		Junior Staff	12
		Non-Core Staff	26
		Total	=44
		First Bank Total	=178
		Grand Total	386

Source: Researchers' computation, 2022

The study employed Yamane's formula (1967) to determine a sample size of 196. The study used a structured questionnaire on a five-point Likert scale to gather relevant information

from the respondents. The study adopted face and content validity while Cronbach alpha was used to ensure the reliability of the instrument at 0.947.

IV. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Table 4.1: Responses to questions in relationship that exists between technical capacity and task accomplishment of selected QDMBs

S/N	Items	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	Remark
	Technical Capacity							
1.	There are programs organized by my organization for to boost our skills.	65	62	13	21	14	3.8	Agree
2.	We have been able to upgrade to modern ways of operations.	43	74	3	32	23	3.5	Agree
3.	I can operate the machines in my department.	54	36	11	66	8	3.35	Agree
	Task Accomplishment							
4.	I complete my task without delay.	51	58	5	42	19	3.5	Agree
5.	I concentrate on my job roles to meet the target.	61	76	5	15	18	3.84	Agree
6.	I am comfortable with my roles in this organization.	43	61	12	36	23	3.37	Agree
	Grand Mean						3.56	Agree

Researchers Computations, 2022

Table 4.1 revealed that respondents agree to questions relating to the relationship between technical capacity and task accomplishment with a grand mean of 3.56.

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Table 4.2: Correlation between adaptive capacity and employee effectiveness of QDMBs

S/N	Items	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	Remark
	Adaptive Capacity							
1.	I prefer to use machines to do my job in this organization.	68	69	7	17	14	3.91	Agree
2.	We have been able to upgrade some old tools to the new ones.	63	79	13	12	8	4.0	Agree
3.	I can readily fill any role in this organization.	31	39	11	64	30	2.87	Disagree
	Employee Effectiveness							
4.	I carry out my duties effectively.	54	30	15	47	29	3.1	Agree
5.	I assist in the execution of the task.	51	46	10	43	25	3.3	Agree
6.	I easily take up challenging task	93	29	7	29	18	3.87	Agree
	Grand Mean						3.51	Agree

Researchers Computations, 2022

Table 4.2, revealed that respondents agree to questions relating to the relationship between adaptive capacity and employee effectiveness with a grand mean of 3.51. Respondents disagreed with fitting into any roles of the organization with an average of 2.87.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis one

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between technical capacity and task accomplishment of QDMBs in Nigeria.

Correlation between technical capacity and task accomplishment of QDMBs

Correlations

		Technical_capacity	Task_accomplishment
Technical_capacity	Pearson Correlation	1	.023
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.017
	N	175	175
Task_accomplishment	Pearson Correlation	.023	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.017	
	N	175	175

Result Summary

Table 4.3.2 above revealed that there is a significant relationship between technical capacity and task accomplishment of selected QDMBs with $r=0.023$, $n=175$, and a p -value of 0.017 ($p<0.5$). As a result, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate Hypothesis. The study, therefore, concludes that there is a significant positive

relationship between technical capacity and task accomplishment of QDMBs in Nigeria

Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between adaptive capacity and employee effectiveness of QDMBs in Nigeria

Table 4.3.3 Correlation between Adaptive Capacity and Employee Effectiveness

Correlations

		Adaptive_capacity	Employee_effectiveness
Adaptive_capacity	Pearson Correlation	1	.052**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.041
	N	175	175
Employee_effectiveness	Pearson Correlation	.052**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.041	
	N	175	175

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Result Summary

Table 4.3.3 above revealed that there is a significant relationship between adaptive capacity and employee effectiveness with $r=0.052$, $n=175$, and a p -value of 0.041 ($p<0.5$). As a result, we reject the null hypothesis and then accept the alternate hypothesis. The study, therefore, concludes that there is a significant negative relationship between adaptive capacity and employee effectiveness of QDMBs in Nigeria.

V. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

The study's hypotheses were tested, and it was discovered that there is a substantial link between capacity building and employee performance of QDMBs in Nigeria.

Table 4.3.2 reveals that technical competence and task completion of QDMBs in Nigeria have a significant relationship. This means that technical capacity determines the knowledge and skills required to complete a task.

Table 4.3.3 reveals that, with $r=0.052$, $n=175$, and a p -value of 0.041 , there is a significant association between adaptive capacity and employee effectiveness. This means that an employee's ability to adapt adds to their performance to some level.

5.2 Conclusion

It may be inferred, based on the outcomes of this study, that capacity building improves employee performance in banks. The study concluded that building employee capacity is equivalent to improving employee performance. The study also concluded that leadership capacity is the level of influence that a manager has over his subordinate staff. It can be deduced that technical capacity has a direct effect on task accomplishment. When an employee has the right knowledge of their roles on the job, the accomplishment of task is guaranteed. Technical capacity implies developing employee skills and job knowledge towards the task. Lastly, employees with high adaptive capacity can function in any changing situation. Adaptive capacity is vital in times of change and employees with high adaptive capacity can cope with changes both technological changes and environmental changes.

The study concluded that building employee capacity is equivalent to improving employee performance. The study also concluded that leadership capacity is the level of influence that a manager has over his subordinate staff. It can be deduced that technical capacity has a direct effect on task accomplishment. When an employee has the right knowledge of their roles on the job, the accomplishment of task is guaranteed. Technical capacity implies developing employee skills and job knowledge towards the task. Lastly, employees with high adaptive capacity can function in any changing situation. Adaptive capacity is vital in times of change and

employees with high adaptive capacity can cope with changes both technological changes and environmental changes.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study proposed the following recommendation

Employees ought to be evaluated to ascertain the gap in their skill set of employees. This will equip employees to accomplish a task without drawbacks.

There should be a strategy in place to instill adaptive capacity in employees. This will assist employees to be effective even in times of change.

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